

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Resource Evaluation of Literature Compounds as PTK2b/PYK2 Chemical Probes

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Introduction:

Protein tyrosine kinase 2 beta (PTK2B), also known as focal adhesion kinase 2 (FAK subfamily member) or proline-rich tyrosine kinase 2 (PYK2), is a non-receptor tyrosine kinase that plays a critical role in calcium-induced regulation of ion channels and activation of the MAPK signaling pathway.¹ It is highly expressed in the central nervous system.² The PYK2 is characterized by distinct domains crucial for its varied functional roles (**Figure 1A**). The protein features a central kinase domain, which is flanked by a FERM (F for 4.1 protein, E for ezrin, R for radixin, and M for moesin) domain at the N-terminus and a proline-rich C-terminus.³ The FERM domain plays an essential role in membrane localization and interaction with other membrane-bound proteins. The kinase domain is responsible for its enzymatic activity, while the proline-rich C-terminal domain provides sites for protein-protein interactions, involving SH3 domain-containing proteins like Src-family kinases.^{1,4} These domains collectively enable PYK2 to act as an integrative hub for diverse signaling pathways, suggesting its complex role in cellular function.⁵

Similar to FAK, PYK2 has an autophosphorylation site in the FERM-kinase linker (Tyr402). Phosphorylation at this site initiates the kinase's activation (**Figure 1B**).³ The autophosphorylation is primarily induced by extracellular signals that raise the levels of intracellular Ca²⁺. These signals stimulate calcium-dependent isoforms of protein kinase C (PKC).¹ However, the exact mechanism by which PKC induces PYK2 Tyr402 autophosphorylation remains unknown. The autophosphorylation of Tyr402 allows interactions with the SH2 domains of the Src family kinases, such as c-Src, Fyn, Lck, Lyn, and Yes. When Src family kinases (SFKs) bind to PYK2 via SH2 and SH3 domains, they are expected to be activated by shedding their autoinhibited conformation.³ These activated SFKs then phosphorylate several tyrosine residues in PYK2, including Tyr579, and Tyr580 in the activation loop, enhancing its kinase activity. In addition, the activated SFKs also phosphorylate Tyr881 in the FAT domain. Depending on the cell type, various signaling pathways can be triggered by the activation of PYK2 through SFK-mediated phosphorylation and interactions with multiple partners. It has also been noted that SFKs might directly phosphorylate Tyr402, suggesting a priming role for subsequent autophosphorylation. The inhibition of

PYK2 activity results from dephosphorylation by protein tyrosine phosphatases (PTPs) such as SHP1 and SHP2.⁶ However, the STEP, also known as protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 5, appears to be the main enzyme that is responsible for binding to PYK2 and catalyzing the dephosphorylation of Tyr402, causing deactivation.⁷ Downstream signaling events resulting from PYK2 activation involve the phosphorylation of PYK2-associated p130Cas and paxillin through PYK2-bound SFKs. They also involve interactions with Grb2 via the PYK2 phospho-Tyr881 site, establishing a connection between G protein-coupled receptors and ERK activation.⁶ These events ultimately lead to influencing cellular functions such as migration, adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation. Interestingly, its function extends to the central nervous system, where it has been implicated in synaptic plasticity and memory formation.⁸

Figure 1. Domain structure of PYK2 enzyme (**A**) and the activation, inhibition, and interactions of PYK2 (**B**)

Several genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have identified PYK2 as a new susceptibility locus for late-onset Alzheimer's Disease (AD), underscoring its pivotal role in AD.⁹ The direct binding of PYK2 to Tau *in vitro*, as well as its co-localization with hyper-phosphorylated Tau in the hippocampi of PYK2 and Tau transgenic mice and in the brains of AD patients, has been documented in the literature.¹⁰ Recently, Giralt et al. reported that the overexpression of PYK2 ameliorates a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease.¹¹ Conversely, other studies in the literature have presented opposing viewpoints.¹² While the role of PYK2 in the context of Tau hyperphosphorylation and A β plaque formation has been explored, it remains pertinent to assess PYK2's influence on other AD-related mechanisms, such as TREM2-mediated microglial activation and phagocytosis. However, it is unclear whether activation or inhibition of PYK2 is necessary to enhance TREM2-mediated microglia activation and phagocytosis. As an initial step, we decided to validate the efficacy and selectivity of several PYK2 selective inhibitors reported in the

literature, using the Hotspot kinase assay format to facilitate the direct comparison. We subsequently assessed their impact in our HMC3 and BV2 phagocytosis assays, and we are reporting the results herein.

Figure 2. Chemical structures of the literature compounds used in this study

Results:

We initially conducted a comprehensive literature survey and identified two potent PYK2-selective inhibitors and one FAK/PYK2 dual-selective inhibitor. Additionally, we included three FAK-selective inhibitors to serve as controls in our phagocytosis assay. Given that the activation of PYK2 largely depends on extracellular signaling events elevating intracellular calcium levels, we also incorporated three spleen tyrosine kinase (SYK) selective inhibitors into the study. This inclusion aims to distinguish the

phenotypic outcome of PYK2 inhibition from that of SYK inhibition. SYK is recognized for initiating activation cell signaling associated with intracellular calcium levels by binding to phosphorylated ITAMs of immune receptors and phosphorylating its downstream targets. As a result, the inhibitors used in this study are categorized as PYK2-selective,^{13, 14} FAK/PYK2 dual-selective,¹⁵ FAK-selective,¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and SYK-selective¹⁹⁻²¹. The chemical structures of these inhibitors, along with their literature-reported inhibitory activities, are presented in **Figure 2**. To facilitate a direct comparison, we first evaluated the PYK2, FAK, SYK and ZAP70 inhibitor activities of these compounds using the Hotspot kinase assay according to a previously described protocol.²² The corresponding substrate was first prepared in a freshly constituted base reaction buffer (20 mM Hepes (pH 7.5), 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM EGTA, 0.01% Brij35, 0.02 mg/ml BSA, 0.1 mM Na₃VO₄, 2 mM DTT, 1% DMSO) and necessary cofactors were introduced to the substrate solution. After that, the kinase was added, ensuring gentle mixing for a homogeneous solution. Using the Echo550 acoustic technology, inhibitors dissolved in 100% DMSO (10 mM) were introduced into the kinase-substrate-cofactor mixture in nanoliter volumes to create a 10-point, three-fold dilution series starting from 100, 10, or 1 μM inhibitor concentrations. This mixture was subsequently incubated at room temperature for 20 minutes to facilitate optimal interactions. The kinase reaction was initiated by adding 33P-ATP (10 μM) into the mixture. Following this, the reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 hours at room temperature to ensure completion. After the incubation, the kinase activity was detected using the P81 filter-binding method. The measured K_i values are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Evaluation of the inhibitor activities of the literature compounds

Comp:	Common Name	Ref	K_i (nM)			
			FAK	PYK2	SYK	ZAP70
1	NA (ref1)	14	144.12	34.4	1089	27900
2	PF-719 (ref2)	13	19.0	12.8	1050	34410
3	PF-562271 (ref3)	15	<4.2	<3.0	312.0	42022
4	PF-04554878 (ref4)	16	<4.2	<3.0	89.6	58147
5	VS-4718/PND-1186	18	<4.2	13.3	60509	ND
6	PF-573228	17	<4.2	70.8	27.1	842.2
7	Lanraplenib/GS-9876	21	29.8	931.8	<4.6	1501
8	NA (ref1)	19	617.7	3332.4	5.2	3108
9	Cevidopenib/SLIO-703	20	16900.	8928.0	<4.6	1732

The IC₅₀ values were determined using the Hotspot kinase assay and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation to facilitate direct comparison. (n = 1)

According to the results, the two PYK2-specific inhibitors retained their literature-reported activities and displayed selectivity over FAK. Notably, compound **1** exhibited a PYK2 inhibitory activity of 34.4 nM with a 4-fold selectivity over FAK. Moreover, both compounds demonstrated pronounced

selectivity for PYK2 over SYK and ZAP70. The dual inhibitor, PYK2/FAK compound **2**, displayed potent activities with K_i values of less than 3.0 nM for PYK2 and 4.2 nM for FAK. Among the three FAK-specific inhibitors (relative to PYK2) evaluated in this study, compounds **5** and **6** exhibited selective inhibition of FAK over PYK2 in the hotspot kinase assay with K_i values of less than 4.2 nM. However, compound **6** also potently inhibited SYK, showing a K_i value of 27.1 nM, indicating a broad-spectrum kinase inhibitor activity not previously documented for this compound in the literature. The literature reported FAK selectivity (over PYK2) for compound **4** couldn't be confirmed due to its robust inhibition of both FAK and PYK2, yielding K_i values of <4.2 nM and <3.0 nM respectively. Hence, among the three FAK selective compounds, only compound **5** demonstrated over 3-fold selectivity for FAK relative to PYK2, while also achieving a significant selectivity of >14406-fold over SYK. All three SYK-selective inhibitors (**7**, **8**, **9**) in this study potently inhibited SYK with activities of <5 nM and maintained a significant selectivity over FAK and PYK2.

Figure 3. Phagocytosis assay curves for 1 and 2 (n =1)

As a preliminary study, next we tested these compounds in BV2 and HMC3 phagocytosis assays to evaluate the impact of selective PYK2 inhibition on microglial activation and phagocytosis. A phenotypic high-content imaging assay with simultaneous measures of phagocytosis, cell number, and nuclear intensity was used to assess both cellular pharmacology and cell health.²³ Model cell lines BV2 (immortalized mouse microglia, a gift from Dr. Michelle Block's laboratory at IUSM) and HMC3

(immortalized human microglia, obtained from ATCC, CRL-3304) were used to provide adequate throughput. Cells were cultured in DMEM GlutaMax media (ThermoFisher) containing 10% FBS and Pen-Strep in a 37°C 5% CO₂ incubator, plated in Corning Falcon 384 well Optilux Black and clear bottom plates; 400 cells/45 µl/well (BV2 cells), 600 cells/45 µl/well (HMC3 cells) and 2000 cell/45 µl/well (primary cells), and treated with 10x serially diluted compounds (60 µM–3 nM) for 48 hrs at 37°C. The cells were then seeded with pHrodo-myelin (20 hrs total) 24 hrs after compound treatment initiation; 1 mg/ml (protein equivalent) pHrodo-myelin stocks were stored at -20°C or -80°C, thawed, diluted with culture media to produce a 10x seeding solution (50 µg/ml) and added to the 384-well plate (5 µl/well). Nuclear staining solution (1 µl of 10 mg/ml Hoechst-33342 per 1 ml culture media; 20 µl/well) was added to a final concentration of 2.5 µg/ml, and the plates were incubated for 30 min at 37°C and then scanned with an ArrayScan automatic high content imaging system (10x objective lens, 4 fields/well collected). Mean total phagocytosis spot intensity per cell, total cell counts per well, and mean average nuclear intensity per cell for cell health were measured. Cellular potencies for each endpoint (EC₅₀ for phagocytosis, IC₅₀ for cell count) were calculated using a four-parameter logistic curve regression model.

None of the compounds discussed in the study were able to induce or inhibit phagocytosis activities in BV2 or HMC3 cells, regardless of their selective inhibition of PYK2, FAK, or SYK, except **1** and **2**. Compounds **1** and **2** induced phagocytosis in HMC3 cells only at higher concentrations, where the cell count also significantly decreased, indicating cytotoxicity (**Figure 3**). This is an interesting observation because **1** and **2** are the two inhibitors found to be PYK2-selective (over FAK). However, further studies are needed to distinguish this phagocytosis-inducing activity from the cytotoxic effect. Furthermore, it might be essential to use a model system where phagocytosis is solely governed by TREM2 signaling. Overall, in this work, we were able to evaluate the kinase activity of literature-reported inhibitors in the Hotspot kinase platform, facilitating their direct comparison. Moreover, we established compounds **1** and **5** as potent and selective inhibitors for PYK2 and FAK, respectively similar to literature reports. Additionally, we validated compounds **7**, **8**, and **9** as selective SYK inhibitors over FAK and PYK2.

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